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MEDIATION & DISPUTE BOARD RESOLUTION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we investigated the existing knowledge on Mediation, Dispute Resolution, and Dispute Board aiming to map the subjects' evolution during the last century through collaborative networks. N = 3,230 publication records were extracted from Scopus and Google Scholar databases through keyword searching, resulting in approximately two million citations. We performed a bibliometric analysis, including text network, citation, trend, and content analysis, revealing themes in the field. The findings are helpful to scholars, students, leaders, and other practitioners, to gain a deeper understanding of the timeline, geographical spread, and development of the subjects. A careful content analysis revealed that the scholarly research revolves mainly around three themes: Mediation, Dispute Resolution, and Dispute Board. Furthermore, the number of citations on the subjects has tripled in the last two decades and is expected to double in the coming decades. Additionally, this paper makes suggestions for further investigation.

KEYWORDS

Mediation, Dispute Resolution, Dispute Board, Systematic Literature Review.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Conflicts are part of human nature. Particles collide, and interests are not met. Therefore, dispute Resolution (DR) is a mechanism designed to address disputes. Despite its relevance to the current epistemology on the subject, some relevant aspects remain to be clarified through the following questions: RQ1: How has Dispute Resolution been cited over the last 120 years? RQ2: What DR themes and subthemes are the most prominent and cited? RQ3: What are the leading Publications in the field? RQ4: What is the geographical spread and development of DR?

Mediation, Dispute Resolution (DR), and Dispute Board (DB) have attracted scholars' attention over the past decades (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011; Olson Jr, 1971; Nozick,1974; Hayek, 2009; Fisher, Ury, Patton, 2011; Reich, 2010; Lind & Tyler,1988; Kirschner, Sweller& Clark, 2006; Asad, 2003; Baker, Bloom, Davis, 2016), for instance.

To answer the RQs, and improve the relevance of the Dispute Resolution research field by investigating the global scientific research on the subject, identifying influential research studies based on Citation networks, and text network analysis to provide emerging trends. Thus, we addressed the research questions through multiple methods approach, combining literature review with content, citation, and text network analysis, described in the upcoming sections.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research, we adopted a systematic literature review (SLR) approach to be described in the following sections (Denyer and Tranfield 2009). Then, the selection was based on its widespread acceptance in bibliometric evaluations. (Cheng et al. 2018; Prashar et al. 2020; Singh and Walia 2020). The methodology is described in depth in the following subsections.

2.1. Review Objectives

We established the review's goals under Goyal and Kumar (2020), with the primary goal of mapping the body of knowledge on leadership. Additionally, we organized the study goals into sub-objectives following Zahoor & Talba's (2020) model, which included (i) mapping the leading publications on the topics and (ii) identifying important research papers using citation network and text network analysis to present new trends in the field. Finally, Table 1 summarizes the review objectives:

Table 1 Sources per theme

Source/Exclusion	Mediation	Dispute Resolution	Dispute Board	Total
Scopus + Google Scholar	1.200	1.200	1.200	3.600
Exclusions	23	224	123	370
Total Valid sources	1.177	976	1.077	3.230

2.2. Research Strategy

The comprehensive literature study revealed Nearly two million citations, which included 3,600 articles. The software Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007) was also used by us to look at the research coverage from 1900 to the present. Only English-language terms were included in the search criteria. Next, Google Scholar was chosen as the academic dataset rather than Web of Science or

Scopus, both of which need a signature and are limited. Per consultation session, Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007) permits 1,000 results. Following the first round, the most relevant emergent topics were determined using a text network analysis, and these themes served as keyword entries in the subsequent iterative cycle. The data were then subjected to a text network and content analysis. Through Google, My Maps®, the new patterns were also spatially examined (see Figure 4).

2.3. Screening and Selection

First, using the program described above with the default search settings of including articles and excluding patents, we looked into the terms "Mediation," "Dispute Resolution," and "Dispute Board." The search included 3,600 articles; 3,230 items were inspected, and 370 were excluded due to duplications. There were also 1,817,818 citations, as shown in Table 1.

Table 2 Number of citations per theme (group)

Theme	Mediation	Dispute Resolution	Dispute Board	Total
Total	227.760	733.362	856.696	1.817.818

2.4. Data Analysis

After three themes emerged throughout the iterative process, four sessions were required to complete the study results. Table 3 describes the study design: Group 1: Mediation; Group 2: Dispute Resolution; Group 3: Dispute Board. The topics were grouped into groups and subgroups and classified according to significance.

Table 3 Research Design

3. BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

3.1. Trend Analysis

Figure 1 indicates a yearly number of publications in the fields of business, administration, covering Mediation, Dispute Resolution, and Dispute Board. The study into this domain is uneven between 1900 and 2023.

Figure 1 Publishing trend in the field of Mediation, Dispute Resolution, and Dispute Board

Figure 2 Publishing trend in the field of Leadership: themes's distribution

Observe that *Dispute Board* is the topic most cited over the past two decades, with 41 percent of the entire citations, as illustrated in the following Figure 2:

Figure 2 Publishing in the field of Leadership: topic distribution (1900-2023)

The distribution of citations from 1900 to 2023 is shown in Figure 3 using information acquired from Google Scholar and Scopus. More than three times as often as Mediation and only behind Dispute Board (47 percent), Dispute Resolution is the second most frequently stated subject (40 percent). A specific dimension of the reference’s publications, particularly in this academic work, is provided by Figures 1 and 2.

Table 4 shows the screening results, organized into themes.

Table 4 Screening results: number of citations per theme

Timeline	Mediation	Dispute Resolution	Dispute Board	Total
1900-1949			13.095	13.095
1950-1969	3.327	1.313	31.052	35.692
1970-1979	7.323	37.103	142.660	187.086
1980-1989	16.954	122.149	161.103	300.206
1990-1999	35.328	310.829	255.508	601.665
2000-2009	164.828	300.384	440.085	905.297
2010-2023	190.549	159.296	296.898	646.743
Total	227.760	733.362	856.696	1.817.818

Next, we gathered Publications’ affiliations from the .csv file saved from Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007). Using <https://www.google.com/intl/pt-BR/maps/about/mymaps/> (Google My Maps), the geographical distribution of the leading publishers is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Geographical location of all contributing organizations.

3.2. Author influence

The most influential contributors to the field of Leadership are introduced in Table 5, which illustrates the most influential publications.

Table 5 top 10 Publications

Rank	Citations	Author(s)	Year
1	86.368	NK Denzin, YS Lincoln	2011
2	53.870	M Olson Jr	1971
3	28.404	R Nozick	1974
4	22.007	FA Hayek	2009
5	15202	R Fisher, WL Ury, B Patton	2011
6	11.840	RB Reich	2010
7	11.581	EA Lind, TR Tyler	1988
8	9.721	PA Kirschner, J Sweller, RE Clark	2006
9	9.567	T Asad	2003
10	9.447	ME Porter, VE Millar	1985

3.3. Network text analysis

A network map of the keywords, titles, and abstracts was utilized to find the thematic clusters on the presumption that terms grouped may represent similar subjects. The network text analysis is shown in Figure 5 and used normalization and density-based spacing clustering techniques. We created a network graph from the text-based data using www.infrandus.com, which revealed insights and trends based on the network characteristics, mainly including the phrases "Mediation," "Dispute Board," and "Dispute Resolution." Keep in mind that each hue denotes a cluster. As a result, the current topics and developing trends in the area were discovered by carefully going through the research articles in each cluster.

independent individuals. The critical distinction between Dispute Review Boards and most other Alternative Dispute Review methods—and perhaps the reason for our Dispute Review Boards' recent success—is that the Dispute Review Board is appointed at the beginning of a project before any disputes arise and actively involved throughout the project (and perhaps any agreed-upon period after that) by making regular site visits. DB reached a peak of citations during the 2000s in this research but is still the most cited of the three themes investigated.

4. DISCUSSION

The present research attempts to throw more light to the Mediation and Dispute Resolution literature providing an overview on the themes Mediation, DR, and DB - the most cited in this study. The systematic review extracted relevant information on the existing literature, and keeping in mind the evidence gathered in the present research, we share some observations and discuss implications for future studies. Firstly, the answer to the research questions RQ1, RQ2, RQ3, and RQ4 is introduced.

RQ1: How has Dispute Resolution been cited over the last 120 years?

The answer to RQ1 is shown in Figure 1. Over the past century, Dispute Resolution is a topic that has been widely studied in the past century, especially from the 1990s to date (see Figure 1)

Table 4 shows that DR performed in this research 733,362 citations from Google Scholar, and Scopus databases from 1900 to date.

RQ2: What DR themes and subthemes are the most prominent and cited?

Table 4 shows the solution to RQ2. According to the evidence, three topics are most often applicable and referenced: 1,817,818 citations were made for 3,230 good sources, including 227,760 for mediation, 733,362 for dispute resolution, and 856,696 for the dispute board. Less cited theories or theories already cited elsewhere distorted the results because some authors published more than one topic in a single article (some literature reviews, for example). Nevertheless, the laborious procedure needs to be more conclusive and error-free.

RQ3: What are the leading Publications in the field?

Table 5 illustrates the top10 publications in the field. Denzin & Lincoln (2011) is the leading publication with 86,368 citations to date.

RQ4: What is the geographical spread and development of DR?

Figure 3 displays the response to RQ4 in full. The geographic distribution mainly includes the continents of North America and Europe. There is evidence to support the claim that the United States is the top-citing nation in several cases. However, only English-language articles were looked into. Therefore, further research is required to determine the worldwide impact of different languages on dispute resolution.

5. Implications and Research limitations

This article is limited to Dispute Resolution, Mediation, and Dispute Board, referenced most during the last 123 years. This research has implications and repercussions for many fields of study, such as (i) business negotiations (Dias et al., 2022; Dias, M., 2020; Dias, M, Leitão, R., Batista, R., Medeiros, D. 2022; Cunha&Dias, M., 2021; Dias, M., 2020b); (ii) teleworking (Schimtz& Dias, M., 2023); (iii) banking (Dias, Pereira, and Vieira, 2022); (iv) Remote leadership (Dias, Pereira, Vieira, and Pan, 2022); (v) information security and leadership (Vieira & Dias, 2022); (vi) virtual teaching (Dias and Lopes, 2020; Dias, Lopes and Teles, 2020); (vii) retail business (Dias & Falconi, 2018).

Finally, this work is helpful to scholars, leaders, decision-makers, policy makers, and other practitioners.

6. Conclusion and Future research

The literature review advanced by earlier academics in the discipline and related citations served as the foundation for the themes that emerged from the literature study. The systematic literature study identified an upward trend in Dispute Board citations over the last three decades (see Figure 1), indicating that DR's citation count may double over the next two decades.

By understanding leadership ideas via methodical literature evaluations, we may remove some of the confusion that has plagued leadership studies for over a century and pave the way for further investigation. Additionally, practice and examination will improve as practitioners and analysts collaborate to develop consensus opinions on these complex subjects. This article will also increase the theoretical underpinning for subsequent actions and estimates and progress research into usually overlooked regions. Global academics have contributed to the area, and Dispute Resolution, Mediation, and Dispute Board have gained popularity over the last four decades. Future research in other disciplines, including databases and languages, is also invited.

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